

PHYSICO-CHEMICAL STUDIES ON HAEMOLYSIN, PART II.

pH AND HEAT STABILITY OF HAEMOLYSIN.

BY S. S. DE,

The effect of p_H and of heating has been determined on crystalline haemolysin. It has been found that haemolysin is most stable at p_H 6.0 and the critical inactivation temperature of haemolysin is observed to be 62°.

The effect of hydrogen-ion concentration and heat on the activity of various crystalline enzymes have been extensively studied and are of importance in determining the characteristics of an enzyme. There are some enzymes which are very sensitive to variations in p_H and temperature while others are not so much affected. These observations might lead to some conclusions as to the nature of the bond involved in the structure of the protein molecule. In some cases it has been observed that in moderately alkaline solution an enzyme is inactivated, but again on neutralising it the activity is partially restored. The active enzyme which is termed a colloidal complex is broken up in alkaline solution and recombines on neutralising the solution.

Heat also inactivates enzymes, but while some enzymes are very sensitive even to a temperature of 50°, others are not much affected even at a temperature of 80°. So a term has been introduced called the half inactivation temperature at which the activity of the enzyme is reduced to one-half of the original value within 60 minutes. The effect of hydrogen-ion concentration and of heating has been determined on crystalline haemolysin (De, *Ann. Biochem. Expt. Med.*, 1944, 4, 45), which has been found to be enzymic in nature.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Effect of p_H . For the purpose of determining the effect of p_H on the activity, 0.2% solution of once crystallized haemolysin from *Naja Tripudians* (variety monocellate) was made in normal saline. 5 C.c. of this solution were transferred to each of a number of flasks and adjusted to different p_H values by the addition of hydrochloric acid or caustic soda solution. For adjusting to p_H 1 and 13, equal volume of 0.2 N acid or alkali were respectively added to the haemolysin solution.

The volume in the different flasks was made up to 10 c.c. by dilution with normal saline. The activity was determined immediately and afterwards at definite intervals of time, the solutions being kept all the time in the refrigerators at 4°. Before determining the activity, the different solutions were brought to p_H 7.4 and then dilutions were made with physiological saline. The units of haemolysin contained

in the different flasks were determined after intervals of 24 hours, 3 days and 6 days. For this purpose a fresh haemolysin solution was prepared each day and activities present in the different flasks were calculated in per cent of the original. To test whether alkali-denatured haemolysin can be reactivated, 50 c.c. of the above haemolysin solution which was kept at p_H 13.0 for 72 hours was neutralised with hydrochloric acid to p_H 6.0 and kept in the refrigerator at 4° for a long period and its activity determined from time to time. But the denatured haemolysin did not regain even a negligible part of its original activity.

TABLE I

Effect of p_H on crystalline haemolysin.

p_H .	Activity present in % of the original		
	24 hours	3 days	9 days
1.0	94	85	70
3.0	97	90	82
4.5	98.5	96	92
6.0	100	99	98.5
7.5	96	85	68
9.0	90	68	45
13.0	82	48	22

TABLE II

Effect of heat on crystalline haemolysin.

Temp.	Activity in % of the original
50°	76.8
60	54.6
62	50.2
70	23.8
80	8.5

Effect of Heating.—For studying the effect of heating, the same 0.2% solution of crystalline haemolysin from *Naja Tripudians* (variety monocellate) was used and the p_H of the solution was adjusted to p_H 6.0. 10 C.c. portions were transferred to different test tubes, and they were heated at different temperatures for a period of 60 minutes. The solutions were cooled and their activity determined with respect to the original venom. It was found that the activity was about half destroyed at 62°.

For purpose of comparison a 0.2% solution of crude *Naja Tripudians* (variety monocellate) venom was heated at 62° for 60 minutes and its activity determined. But instead of diminished activity its activity was slightly enhanced and found to be 101.5% in comparison with crude venom.

The crystalline haemolysin solution which was inactivated at 62° for 60 minutes was kept in the refrigerator at 4° for 24 hours and the activity of the sample was then determined. It was found that the inactivated product regained a portion of its original activity. The activity of the sample was 52.6% of the original, against its initial activity 50.2% of the original. Thus an increase of 2.4% of the total activity has been obtained by keeping the heat inactivated product in the cold.

It is observed that crystalline haemolysin is most stable at p_H 6.0 and is inactivated both in acid or alkaline solution. The rate of inactivation in the alkaline solution is much greater than in comparable concentration of acid solution. On neutralising alkali-inactivated solution, no regaining of the activity was observed.

Heating also inactivates haemolysin to a moderate degree and half-inactivation temperature of crystalline haemolysin was found to be 62° . But the haemolysin in crude venom was not inactivated by heating at 62° , rather the activity was slightly increased. This is probably due to the fact that some other inert protein, which is acting as an inhibitor, is absorbed on haemolysin molecules in crude venom, and the inert protein protects the haemolysin molecules from the effect of heat, it being denatured preferentially to the haemolysin.

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PHYSICO-CHEMICAL STUDIES ON HAEMOLYSIN. PART III. ISO-ELECTRIC POINT OF HAEMOLYSIN

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The iso-electric point of crystalline haemolysin has been determined both by the micro-cataphoretic method and the U-tube method and has been found to be at p_H 8.55 by the first method and 8.61 by the second method.

Of the different properties which characterise an enzyme, the determination of the iso-electric point is of considerable importance. Every protein molecule has a charge, which depends on the reaction of the medium in which it is dissolved. The p_H at which the charge of the protein is practically nil is called the iso-electric point of the protein. The iso-electric point coincides with a minimum for many of the physico-chemical properties of a protein, including cataphoresis, conductivity, solubility and osmotic pressure. The iso-electric point is affected by the buffer used for the measurement, since the charge on a colloidal particle may be affected not only by hydrogen ion but also by other ions present. It is known that if a protein solution is shaken with colloidal particles, the particles adsorb the protein and possess the same charge as that of the protein. It has been shown by Loeb (*J. Gen. Physiol.*, 1923, 6, 105) that iso-electric point of gelatine or of egg-albumin, measured either when in solution or adsorbed on the surface of microscopic particles, gives fairly concordant results. Abramson (*ibid.*, 1932, 15, 575) also compared his results for the electric mobility of serum albumin adsorbed on quartz surface and